

Kansei Engineering in the Scandinavian Design Process

Case Study

Key Themes: Emotional design, Kansei Engineering.

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Abstract

The term Kansei comes from Japanese and describes a mental feeling or an image of a product. Kansei engineering attempts to translate the consumers' feeling about a product into perceptual design elements. The approach is also sometimes referred to as "sensory engineering" or "emotional usability." It involves the decision which sensory attributes generate particular subjective responses. The goal is using the attributes to design a product which incites the desired responses. The case study presented in this text is looking at ways of how to include emotional values into product design through the methodology of Kansei Engineering. The questions to be answered through the project are: Which methods within Kansei Engineering can be deployed in smaller Scandinavian design practices? Is Kansei Engineering a tool which can be used by most designers to link emotions and product properties? Is there a future for Kansei Engineering in Europe?

Keywords: Kansei Engineering, Emotional Design, Industrial Design, Integrating Feelings in the Design Process, Design Methodology, Product Domain, Semantic Space, Space of Properties and Human Factors.

1. Background

The presented project endeavours to integrate elements from the Kansei Engineering Methodology in Scandinavian design practises. The aim was to find out if this methodology is suited for a culture very different from where the Kansei Engineering origins, and which also doesn't have a word equivalent to the word "Kansei". It was also the author's purpose to see if Kansei Engineering could be implemented with fewer resources and still use statistical methods. The interest in the emotional quality of products has risen considerably in the last years perhaps because there is a greater awareness on how powerful emotions are in changing the way we think. (Norman, 2004).

The methods used will not be entirely explained in this paper. Kansei Engineering methods construct models in which emotional responses to design are linked to the product properties. It is a methodology that integrates affective elements already in the developing process. Kansei Engineering has been applied in the design of a variety of products, especially in Japan. This design methodology uses both statistical and manual methods for linking emotions with product properties. A specific Kansei arises when a human is subjected to an artefact in a certain environmental context (Schütte, 2005). It can be described like a complex high grade emotion built up by other emotions and feelings. This case study is dealing with emotions described through Kansei words. KE gives a prediction model where connections between Kanseis and properties are given. This project is a continuation of the case study done in my previous paper about integration of Kansei engineering in the Scandinavian design process. In the case study, conventional battery drills for residential use were analyzed through Kansei methods, resulting in a model linking emotional values through words and product properties.

2. Design Case

In the case study conventional battery drills were analyzed and connections between Kansei words and product properties were identified. Groups of words which users use to describe emotions evoked by conventional battery drills with where found in magazines, manuals, ads,

product reviews, user forums on the internet, brochures and user interviews. Words were chosen because they could be used in a statistical analysis and because many different sources with words were available.

These were grouped into higher Kansei words manually. 51 battery drills were analysed, and different properties categorized. 23 drills representing combinations of these properties were scaled on semantic scales with the Kansei words. Ten students participated in this survey. Some words were found to be connected statistically in an emotional vector space. These were called clusters of Kansei words in an emotional vector space.

2.1 Starting Point

Two clusters of Kansei words were chosen to be explored and possibly expanded further through design of a new battery drill. These clusters represented new trends in battery design which could be explored and possibly expanded into new domains.

Figure 1: KE Model proposed by Schütte (2005).

2.2 Choice of domain

The Product Domain is an expansion of the domain for the conventional drills from the case study. The Kansei Domain can be described as the perfect idea behind a product. This step is done to define and cover a big as possible part of the domain. Choosing the domain is done by selecting a target group, market and specification of the new product. Product samples from within the domain are

collected. A domain also includes concepts and potential solutions that not yet have been developed. Representatives are found and created to cover an as big as possible part of the domain.

2.3 Product Specification

The most important element in the specification was that the drill should represent an expansion into an emotional space identified in the case study.

2.4 Spanning the semantic space

The Kansei Words from the case study were: *Aggressive, Confidence, Freedom, Fun, Futuristic, Lifestyle, Personal, Power and Rugged*. These are words which users employed to describe battery drills. These were collected from sources where users describe battery drills like user interviews, magazines, brochures and user evaluations on the internet.

2.5 Spanning the space of properties

2.5.1 Conceptualizing

New properties were generated through a simplified version of Schütte's three step model. The process consists of three main steps: Collection, Selection and Compiling of data. First new concepts were generated in thumbnail sketches using properties from existing products and new ones. Then those evaluated to be important were included. This was done manually by the author similar to a conventional concept generating.

2.5.2 Chosen Properties

Some of the properties from the conceptualizing were chosen to be included in the Space of Properties. Examples of generated properties are position of assembly screws and rear profiles.

Colour as a property was not included because it would lead to way too many samples in order to get represent all possible combinations of the data.

The new properties were systematically distributed into thirteen concepts representing different combinations.

2.6 User survey

The thirteen concepts representing different combinations of the properties from the Space of Properties were included in a user test. The concepts were evaluated on seven point scales for each Kansei word by ten master students. The data was treated with a one-sample t-test (2-tailed) that showed normal distribution of the data. Neither could any significant variances between genders be identified.

2.7 Factor analysis

The data was treated with a factor analysis to reduce the variables (Kansei words) into factors. The Kanseis converged into three factors. The semantic space can according to Osgood (1969) be generalized into the three factors of *Activity*, *Potency* and *Evaluation*.

Figure 2: Cluster analysis.

2.8 Cluster analysis

The Kansei words were clustered visually. This was because they converged into only three factors which made a three dimensional space where the clusters could be found. The fact that the words could have been grouped similarly without a factor analysis obviously seems to verify the further analysis.

2.9 Cross Tabs

The data was run in a cross tabs analysis which revealed connections between Kansei words and properties which resulted in a model linking Kanseis and properties.

	KanseiWord	ChuchShape	TriggerGroove	EngineHouseFrontScrew	EngineHouseBackScrew	ReverseTrigger	Vents	EngineHouseDetail	BatteryHouse
1	Rugged	-	Groove	Screw	-	-	-	-	-
2	Freedom	-	-	Screw	-	-	-	-	-
3	Futuristic	-	-	Screw	-	-	-	-	No Rectangular
4	Personal	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	Screw on bottom
5	Power	Cone	-	-	-	-	Middle	-	-
6	Lifestyle	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	Screw on bottom
7	Confidence	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	Screw on bottom
8	Fun	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	Screw on bottom
9	Agressive	Cone	-	-	-	-	Middle	-	Screw on bottom

Figure 3: Model linking emotions through words and product properties.

2.10 Further conceptualization

This phase of the process concentrated on implementing all properties found in the model. These were further explored and detailed through sketches and mock-ups.

Figure 4: Further conceptualization.

Figure 5: Foam Mock Up.

2.11 Category Identification

In Category Identification kansei words are manually linked to product properties which would be difficult to include in a visual analysis. Each kansei was linked to different parts of the drill and possible design solutions regarding shape, colour and materials were generated.

Confidence:	Direction in housing. Arrow like shape. Sharp and pointing Chuck.
Freedom:	Balanced look. Handle details like grip metaphor.
Rugged:	Not to skinny shape. Rib elements on battery. Rubberized protection around "soft spots" like the ventilation.
Power:	Battery semantics. Engine House should look "beefed up". Wide Chuck. Dynamic shape.
Fun:	Unconventional colours.
Futuristic:	Unconventional coloured elements.
Lifestyle:	Balanced proportions.
Aggressive:	Sharp and pointing Chuck. Pointing housing. Venomous colour elements. Fire flames?
Personal:	Grip metaphor in shaft. The drill should be welcoming toward the direction in which the user grips the product. Aggressive elements should be facing away from the user.

Figure 6: Model from the Category Identification.

2.12 Further Detailing

Finally all elements from both the statistical models and the manual had been included in the concept. Then detailing regarding mechanical elements and ergonomic issues were tested before the final product was ready.

Figure 7: Detailing

2.13 Final Product

The final product is absolutely a statement of a different but still familiar battery drill. The drill is operated like conventional battery drills.

Figure 8: Drill elevations.

Figure 9: Drill details

3. Implications

3.1 Final user survey

A final survey was done in order to verify if the design process had succeeded in making a product which reflected the chosen kansei words. The product scored high on all kansei words and showed that the final product has succeeded in integrating the nine kansei words in the design.

3.2 Conclusion

Kansei Engineering can clearly be a useful tool in the Scandinavian design practice as the case study and this report indicate. The kansei scores for the final product are definitely verifying this assumption. But what about firms with limited time and resources? They can certainly use a method from Kansei Engineering which are easy to do and which do not rely on expensive software. Some authors claim that Kansei Engineering methods are no different from the semantic transformations and mood board techniques used by European designers. Indeed, Kansei Engineering implements more conventional methods like factor analyses and semantic mapping. But what makes KE unique is that it can give a statistically link between emotions expressed through words and product features. This can sometimes reveal connections that designers cannot see. It is a useful tool for documenting certain choices done in the design process as well. As a methodology Kansei Engineering invites the designer to consider emotional aspects and their relations to a product's attributes through the whole design process. This can also be done with other methods, but KE is a very flexible tool where appropriate methods can be chosen depending on the project. Kansei Engineering is often dealing with kansei words. People in Japan have very different ways of expressing themselves from Scandinavians. Only time will tell if Kansei Engineering will be a part of industrial design processes in Scandinavia. From my point of view it will be important to develop KE methods which are adapted to Scandinavians and their culture. It is also important to take care of the artistic and magical part of design. Experience and emotions should always guide the designer. Not everything should be based on

statistics and theory only. A design process require designers and their ability of creative thinking. Thus KE is not a tool which makes everybody capable of designing products. Experience, creative ideas, visions and inspiration will always be the driving forces in the design process. My opinion is that Kansei Engineering is foremost an additional guiding tool and way of reinforcing your decisions in the process. Kansei Engineering is definitively a useful design tool. I am overall very satisfied with what I learned about Kansei Engineering and emotional design. It was challenging to explore new parts of a product domain, while also be restrained by material and production limitations. I think the final design is a example of how a focused design process can be reflected in the product it self.

References

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